

The Native Speaker

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Abstract

The native Speaker is the original speaker of any language. From the start there are trials to evoke the rampant affairs of speech by the first speaker or the first language the person's speak. Highlighting the continuous blockage of the first language sustain by the aggressiveness of the Media today. As an act of fairness there are accumulation of multilingual individuals these days. Nevertheless, the cultivation of knowledge is through the person's speech or the person's first language. If the writer denies the distribution of certain languages internationally like English, it is suspectable to interfere with the logistic facts or some other political opinion., so let the consideration be knowledge. In fact there are big propaganda about knowing the facts of life deeply, for generations and levels of ethnic groups it can be found some sustainable ideas.

Introduction

As verbal communication it's meant here the strength to communicate through different languages around the world. A native speaker of English can be found any where in the whole world, because if it be depended on the central, the native speaker of English are in Northern America, England and Australia this is dogmatic distribution. A bit more peripheral for example India as a large population, there the Indians speak English with their accents the flow of the image of the Indians' languages. Here it is an example, because this flow or can be said image is all over the world any country from large population to small amount of people.

In consideration to a native speaker definition, it can be defined systematically through the formation of the language itself among its basics from alphabetical formations, grammar, rules of writing, rules of speaking. The Intimacy to hydronation in knowledge to write perfectly and retain it as a native speaker's favorites as a handbook of cocktails if it is tried to be defined. As a native speaker through the thrilling of sounds till the independent writing. It's as if a blockage of measurements applying decodes everywhere. If here shedding light on the most atmospheric gender knowledge the style, the shape and the announcement of being in order or stylish. The continuous dragging of information from, to, in, off, and out. This is like bursting the clients here and there. As it had been said before the rehearsing of knowledge to let the scientific of it to be the leadership of the world. Here it is Knowledge information. So when somebody seeks it here he/she will and has to need another language(s).

At the contemporary the hidden batches of seeking a knowledge lead it to be said a native speaker like. There are of course other establishments.

The question will be :-

Where have you been brought up?

Let the origins alone and the first language vague. The trumpet horn here give other measurements to stablish the focusing of native speaker LIKE. Here as being given evidences of life in its different ways.

Here let us to some Native Speaker meaning (1) & (2)

In language studies, native speaker is a controversial term for a person who speaks and writes using his or her native language (or mother tongue). Put simply, the traditional view is that the language of a native speaker is determined by birthplace. Contrast with *non-native speaker*.

Linguist Braj Kachru identifies native speakers of English as those who have grown up in the "Inner Circle" of countries—Britain, America, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand.

An extremely proficient speaker of a second language is sometimes referred to as a *near-native speaker*.

When a person acquires a second-language at a very young age, the distinction between *native* and *non-native speaker* becomes ambiguous. "A child may be a native speaker of more than one language as long as the acquisition process starts early," says Alan Davies. "After puberty (Felix, 1987), it becomes difficult—not impossible, but very difficult (Birdsong, 1992)—to become a native speaker." (*The Handbook of Applied Linguistics*, 2004).

In recent years, the concept of the native speaker has come under criticism, especially in connection with the study of World English, New Englishes, and English as a Lingua Franca: "While there may be linguistic

differences between native and non-native speakers of English, the native speaker is really a political construct carrying a particular ideological baggage" (Stephanie Hackert in *World Englishes--Problems, Properties and Prospects*, 2009).

The Ideology of the Native Speaker Model

"[T]he notion of 'native speaker'--sometimes referred to as the ideology of the 'native speaker' model—in the field of second language education has been a powerful principle that influences almost every aspect of language teaching and learning . . . The notion of 'native speaker' takes for granted the homogeneity among, and superiority of the linguistic competence of 'native speakers' and legitimizes the unequal power relations between 'native' and 'non-native' speakers."

(Neriko Musha Doerr and Yuri Kumagai, "Towards a Critical Orientation in Second Language Education." *The Native Speaker Concept*. Walter de Gruyter, 2009)

Then let us see the native speaker definition (3)

The trend for learning English has not slowed down for many years, and recently, thanks to new, previously unavailable forms of education, it is even gaining momentum. With online lessons or classes with native speakers, it is much easier for students to stay in touch with a “living” language.

Extracurricular English classes with a native speaker have become extremely popular recently, mainly due to technological development. Currently, all a student needs to connect with an English teacher from another country is a computer with Internet access. The whole meeting takes place without leaving one’s home and commuting anywhere. A teacher for whom English is the first language is called a native speaker. As numerous studies show, an English native speaker online can effectively help a child learn a foreign language!

Find out more about English lessons with a native speaker and who a native speaker is! Find out if English language classes conducted by a native speaker are something that will help your child learn English faster on many levels. Improve your pronunciation skills and get fluent in communication skills if English is your second language. Discover all the benefits of learning with a native speaker and sign up for a free trial lesson at Novakid today. Start sounding like a native speaker! We will tell you where to look for reliable online classes conducted by the best native speakers from around the world!

Who is a native speaker and how do they use English?

A native English speaker is a person for whom English is their mother tongue. This does not mean, however, that a native speaker must necessarily be of British, American or Australian nationality. They may well be representatives of any other nationality living in an English-speaking country on a daily basis and speak English at the same level of proficiency as their mother tongue.

For example, a native speaker may be an English teacher from India or a person who was born in Brazil, but lives most of their life in Great Britain and speaks this language on a daily basis.

With a native speaker, the most important thing is that this person has constant contact with the natural English language, is immersed in a particular language environment and can share their knowledge and experience from everyday life in an English-speaking country with students. It is also worth remembering that the term native speaker does not only refer to English speakers. It applies to every language in the world.

Native Speaker definition in Cambridge dictionary (4)

someone who has spoken a particular language since they were a baby, rather than having learned it as a child or adult:

At last we can see What is Native Speaker – like ? (5)

You know that TV show *Americans*? It’s about a pair of Russian spies who manage to convince everyone they meet that they’re American. Their accent is impeccable and their grammar perfect.

Does this sound believable to you? Can an English learner really learn how to sound like a native speaker? Outside the realm of movies, of course.

I believe that with work and dedication you can improve your pronunciation immensely and, over time, reach a point where your accent in English might differ only slightly from that of a native speaker (or not at all!)

This, of course, depends on the effort you put in. There are people who just have a knack for languages and can pick them up really easily, but even they need a lot of practice to sound like a native. It’s not enough to know the rules of grammar and have an extensive vocabulary – you must also work hard on your pronunciation.

So, whether you want to perfect your English in order to teach English in China, for example, or to move up in your career, or perhaps to become a successful spy, try some of these tips and methods of practice:

1. Immerse yourself in the language

Most of us learned how to speak our native language because we grew up surrounded by people speaking it around us. As children, we acquire language, we don’t learn it. Our brain just picked things up. This changes in adulthood, however, and the process of acquiring a language becomes more difficult.

So, why not “recreate” the childhood conditions? Surround yourself with English as much as you can and let your subconscious pick it up.

If you can’t live in a country where English is spoken as a first language, you can always use technology to your advantage. In this day and age, we have access to an enormous amount of video and audio materials. There are countless TV channels, movies and series, songs, radio shows... Just choose whatever suits you most and play it whenever you can. Do your household chores, eat, play with your pet, and simply let English “flow” into your brain.

Find tips on how you can do this and many more immersion ideas on Linguasorb’s Ultimate Guide to at-home immersion.

2. Pay attention to how your lips and tongue move

Many non-native English speakers need to learn how to pronounce sounds that don’t even exist in their mother tongues. This can sometimes be quite challenging, as it requires your lips and tongue to move in ways that you’re not used to.

To overcome this potential problem, you need to analyze what happens to your lips and tongue when you pronounce certain sounds. To do this, use a trick actors often turn to: stand in front of a mirror. This is by far the simplest way to see what your mouth is doing.

Also, watch closely when native speakers speak. Notice the shapes their mouth and lips make. With movies or TV shows, you can always play certain parts several times to take a really good look.

Now, it’s a bit trickier to see what the tongue does during pronunciation. You need to be aware of how it moves for various sounds and practice adjusting it.

If you’re not sure about the correct position of the tongue for a certain sound, there are many videos, pictures and explanations online that can help you.

3. Imitate

Choose a favorite movie, a clip, or a TV show, play a certain part several times and listen very carefully. Think about the pitch changes and the musicality of the speech and repeat the words exactly as you hear them, even if you’re not sure of the individual words.

4. Add stress to sounds and words

English is a stressed language and sometimes where you put the stress in a word can change the word’s meaning. For example, in American English, the noun “ADDress” is the place where someone lives, while the verb “addRESS” means to speak to someone.

Sentences have stresses too. Some words in a sentence present more important information and are said with more clarity and strength than the rest of the sentence. You slow down when you get to the important words and quickly go over the less important ones.

If you’re not in a position to communicate to native speakers regularly, this too can be practiced using different online programs.

References

(1)&(2)[Native Speaker - Definition and Examples in English \(thoughtco.com\)](https://www.thoughtco.com/definition-of-native-speaker/)

(3)<https://www.novakidschool.com/blog/who-is-a-native-speaker-and-how-to-speak-english-like-a-native/>

(4)[NATIVE SPEAKER | English meaning - Cambridge Dictionary](https://www.cambridge.org/9780521875666/entry/native-speaker)

(5)[How to sound like a Native English Speaker \(linguasorb.com\)](https://www.linguasorb.com/en/how-to-sound-like-a-native-english-speaker)

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